

E-Democratic Tools & Inclusive Democracy in Europe

Transnational United Network in Europe

Introduction

In an era marked by rapid digital transformation, the role of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in democratic processes has gained immense significance. This booklet, *E-Democratic Tools and Inclusive Democracy in Europe*, delves into how digital platforms are reshaping governance and creating more inclusive, transparent, and accountable systems across Europe. E-participation, at the forefront of this movement, empowers citizens by providing them with digital avenues to engage directly with governmental decision-making, influence policy, and advocate for change.

Central to e-participation is the idea that ICT can be used to foster more meaningful interactions between citizens and their governments. The European Commission's focus on digital rights and principles highlights the importance of placing citizens at the center of this transformation, promoting solidarity, freedom of choice, and inclusivity. Through various digital tools, citizens can participate in consultations, contribute to public debates, and engage in policy development processes. This booklet illustrates how e-democracy and e-advocacy tools are helping to bridge the gap between citizens and policymakers, enhancing transparency and trust in political institutions.

Furthermore, the booklet presents practical case studies such as the European Citizens' Initiative (ECI) and Finland's Off-Road Traffic Act Experiment, showcasing how digital tools have been effectively employed in public participation. It also explores the use of anonymized pre- and post-intervention surveys to measure the success of e-participation campaigns while safeguarding participants' privacy.

In addition, this booklet introduces design thinking as a powerful methodology to enhance digital participation platforms. By employing a user-centered, iterative approach, design thinking enables the co-creation of solutions tailored to citizens' needs. The four-stage process—Discover, Define, Develop, and Deliver—guides public institutions and advocacy groups in refining e-participation tools through constant feedback and collaboration.

This booklet is the deliverable of a 4-day online training facilitated by *Marios Iakovidis, ICT expert and PhD candidate in Critical Digital Literacy, Digital Ethics Education* and has been developed as part of the TUNE project, co-funded by the European Union, capturing key practices that foster a more inclusive European democracy through digital civic engagement.

Chapter 1

Understanding e-Democracy & e-Participation

Defining Key Concepts:

- e-participation
- e-advocacy
- e-democracy

E-Participation refers to the involvement of citizens in democratic processes through digital platforms. This concept was reinforced by the European Commission's January 2022 declaration on digital rights and principles for everyone in the European Union, which focuses on "**putting people at the center of the digital transformation; solidarity and inclusion; freedom of choice; participation in digital life; safety and security; and sustainability**". The government's role in e-participation is vital, acting as initiator, moderator, or receiver of digital feedback from the public. According to the United Nations' definition, e-participation involves engaging citizens through ICTs to make governance processes more inclusive, participatory, and deliberative (David Le Blanc, 2020).

Through Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), citizens can participate in various governmental activities such as consultations, public debates, and voting.

ICT includes a wide range of technologies, such as hardware, software, and networks, that support communication and information processing. E-Participation enables transparency, accountability, and trust in political institutions by allowing citizens to engage and influence public policies more directly (European Commission, 2022).

Key Takeaways

e-Participation leverages technology to enable citizen engagement/collaboration in governmental decision-making and service delivery

Key Stakeholders

Source: Trainer's elaboration

- **Citizens:** Through ICT, citizens can participate in governmental decision-making by providing feedback, engaging in public consultations, and contributing to policy discussions. This promotes inclusivity by ensuring that a diverse range of voices is represented.
- **Elected Officials:** Elected officials, acting as representatives of the people, use ICT to both engage with citizens and address their concerns in policymaking. Digital tools enhance transparency and allow elected officials to communicate more directly and effectively with their constituencies.
- **Public Administration:** The role of public administration in e-participation is to implement policies and manage services in response to citizen input. ICT enables public institutions to gather data, analyze trends, and improve service delivery by actively engaging citizens in the process.

Together, ICT serves as the backbone for this collaborative effort, enabling a more transparent and accountable governance.

(Lindner, R., & Aichholzer, G., 2020).

E-Democracy refers to the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) to enhance and support traditional democratic processes by increasing citizen engagement, participation, and transparency in governance. It encompasses various forms of digital interaction between governments and citizens, including online consultations, e-voting, e-participation, and e-initiatives. E-democracy seeks to complement, rather than replace, traditional systems of representative democracy by introducing new channels for civic engagement and providing citizens with more accessible ways to participate in political decision-making (European Parliament, 2017).

In Europe, e-democracy has been particularly emphasized since 2009 with the introduction of digital tools like the European Citizens' Initiative (ECI). The ECI allows citizens to propose legislation to the European Commission, provided they gather one million signatures across at least seven member states. This platform exemplifies how e-democracy fosters inclusive governance by enabling citizens to have a direct say in legislative processes, regardless of their geographical location (European Parliament, 2017). Additionally, public consultations and e-governance platforms enhance citizen participation and government accountability by offering more opportunities for civic engagement in shaping public policies (Lironi, E., 2016).

The Empowerment of Digital Citizenship

Source: Trainer's elaboration

- Citizen Engagement (eParticipation/eAdvocacy): This involves the active participation of citizens in democratic processes through digital means. It includes activities like online voting, e-petitions, and digital forums where citizens can voice their opinions and influence policy decisions.
- Digital Technology (ICT): Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) are the backbone of e-Democracy. These technologies facilitate the interaction between citizens and government, making democratic processes more accessible, efficient, and inclusive.
- Transparent Governance: e-Democracy promotes transparency and accountability in governance by making information more accessible to the public. This includes open data initiatives and online platforms that allow for more open communication between citizens and government.

Bilal, J. T. (2017).

E-Advocacy, a branch of e-Participation, focuses specifically on using digital tools to advocate for policy change and engage citizens in activism. It involves the use of ICT to mobilize citizens, gather public support for a cause, and put pressure on policymakers. E-Advocacy facilitates inclusive participation, allowing diverse voices to be heard through social media, online petitions, and digital campaigns. This form of advocacy ensures that marginalized communities have a platform to express their concerns and advocate for their rights.

However, several challenges remain. One major obstacle is the **digital division**, where lack of access to technology and digital literacy skills can exclude certain populations from participating fully in e-democratic processes. Ensuring secure internet connections, robust digital infrastructures, and educational programs on digital literacy are necessary steps to bridge this gap and promote more inclusive democratic participation. Furthermore, concerns about **cybersecurity** and **data privacy** remain critical, as ensuring the integrity and security of online platforms is essential for building public trust (Tambouris et al., 2013).

Introduction to different levels of e-participation (Empowerment, Consultation, Information Provision, Collaboration)

The levels of e-participation can be understood as a spectrum that reflects the depth of citizen engagement in governmental processes, ranging from basic information provision to full empowerment.

Empowerment

The highest level of e-participation, where citizens play a central role in agenda/setting and decision-making processes. This level involves transferring significant decision-making power to the public.

Collaboration

At this level, citizens, governmental bodies, and non-governmental actors collaborate closely to jointly arrive at decisions or work together on public service delivery. This reflects a more active role for citizens in shaping outcomes.

Consultation

This stage allows citizens to express their views and provide feedback on government actions and decisions. While the government listens to these opinions, the final decision-making power remains with the government.

Information Provision

At this foundational level, governments provide citizens with necessary information regarding public policies, decisions, and services. This is crucial for transparency but represents a one-way communication process.

(United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2020)

Putting it all together

E-participation represents the intersection of technology and democracy, providing citizens with the tools to engage in decision-making processes, offer feedback, and hold governments accountable. As governance continues to evolve in the digital age, the concept of e-participation becomes essential for fostering transparency, inclusivity, and collaboration between public institutions and citizens. By connecting with broader frameworks such as e-government, inclusion, participation, and transparency, e-participation helps bridge the gap between citizens and decision-makers. This model not only encourages a more informed and active civic engagement but also highlights the importance of open access to information, meaningful consultation, and the involvement of marginalized groups through digital inclusion efforts.

Source: https://www.un.org/esa/desa/papers/2020/wp163_2020.pdf

A comprehensive understanding of the potential benefits of e-participation remains elusive, as concrete evidence supporting its positive impact is still limited. This lack of information presents a significant barrier to fully realizing the potential of e-participation.

One of the major questions is who participates in e-participation platforms. Often, these platforms may only engage individuals who are already politically active or have access to the necessary technology, leaving out other diverse groups. This raises concerns about whether e-participation is truly inclusive or whether it reinforces existing inequalities by excluding marginalized populations.

The issue of inclusivity vs. inequality is central to the discussion. While e-participation has the potential to bridge gaps and empower underrepresented voices, it could also exacerbate power imbalances if only those with digital access or the skills to use these platforms can engage effectively.

The quality of participation is also a crucial factor. It's important to ensure that online engagement is not just superficial but meaningful and impactful, contributing to better governance and decision-making processes. This leads to the question of impact on outcomes: does e-participation improve decision-making and service delivery in a tangible way?

For participants, it's essential to understand the benefits of engaging online. What do individuals gain from participating in e-democracy initiatives? Are there concrete outcomes, such as improved public services or stronger representation, or are the benefits more abstract?

Finally, a lack of systematic investigation by governments and organizations into these key questions hinders the development and improvement of e-participation platforms. Rigorous research is needed to address these issues and enhance the effectiveness of e-participation in promoting inclusive, democratic governance (IJAB, 2014).

Bridging the gap

Finland's New Citizens' Initiative Act (2012)

In March 2012, Finland introduced the Citizens' Initiative Act, which allows citizens to propose new legislation or changes to existing laws. To be considered, these petitions must gather 50,000 signatures within six months, either online or through paper forms. Once a petition meets this threshold, the Finnish Parliament is mandated to consider the initiative, providing options to discuss, amend, or reject it.

This initiative offers several benefits, including increased citizen participation in policy-making and engaging the youth demographic. The act also fosters innovative ideas by utilizing the "wisdom of the crowd," encouraging diverse perspectives in legislative proposals.

However, there are challenges to the system. The success rate has been limited, with only one law passed from nine initiatives. The user base also skews towards young, educated, urban males, highlighting issues of privileged access. Consequently, this may not represent the broader population, raising concerns about inclusivity and equity in participation (Council of Europe, 2012).

Finland's Off-Road Traffic Act Experiment (2013)

Finland's Off-Road Traffic Act Experiment (2013) serves as an example of innovative e-participation through crowdsourcing. The process involved an online deliberation platform that encouraged citizens to engage in proposing, commenting on, and voting for topics related to off-road traffic. It included three phases: problem mapping, problem-solving, and evaluation.

This approach promoted transparency and public involvement, using features like anonymous participation and a point system to engage citizens.

Key features of this process included civil and constructive discussions, realistic citizen expectations, learning opportunities, effective crowd evaluation, and the inclusion of minority voices. However, challenges arose, such as the potential for misrepresentation of preferences, limited participation from certain demographics (notably northern males), and a lack of institutionalized processes to ensure that citizen input was formally considered. In the end, the Finnish Minister of Environment made the final decision on the reform.

This crowdsourcing experiment demonstrated both the positive outcomes and challenges of e-participation, particularly in terms of civic engagement, transparency, and inclusivity. However, it highlighted the need for robust institutional frameworks to ensure that such inputs have a tangible influence on policy decisions (Lironi, E., 2016).

Existing e-Participation Tools at the EU level (ECI)

The European Citizens' Initiative (ECI) serves as a key tool for promoting direct citizen participation in EU law-making processes. By empowering EU citizens to propose new legislation or policy changes, the ECI encourages democratic engagement and fosters inclusion across member states.

To launch an initiative, a citizens' committee must be formed, consisting of at least seven members from at least seven different EU member states. After gathering one million signatures from across the EU, the initiative is reviewed by the European Commission. The initiative must fall within the EU's legislative competence and comply with the Commission's framework. If approved, the Commission may propose new legislation to the legislator based on the initiative. This process enhances transparency and allows EU citizens to contribute directly to shaping European policies.

Key steps include:

- Forming a citizens' committee with representation from at least seven member states.
- Gathering at least one million signatures from at least seven EU member states.
- The European Commission evaluates the initiative, and if it meets the requirements, it can lead to new legislation being proposed to the EU legislator.

This approach encourages participation in governance, although challenges, such as obtaining sufficient support and navigating complex legislative requirements, remain prevalent.

European Citizens' Initiative

The screenshot shows the homepage of the European Citizens' Initiative website. At the top is a blue navigation bar with links: Home, Find initiative, How it works, News, Spread the word, For schools, ECI Forum, and Organiser account. Below the navigation bar is the heading "Home". The main content area features a paragraph explaining the ECI: "Get a greater say in the policies that affect your life. The European Citizens' Initiative is a unique way for you to help shape the EU by calling on the European Commission to propose new laws. Once an initiative has reached 1 million signatures, the Commission will decide on what action to take. See how it works step by step." Below this is a link to "See how it works step by step" and a note: "If you consider starting an initiative, consult the ECI Forum for legal and practical advice." To the right is a blue graphic with concentric circles and the text: "The European Citizens' Initiative: Your right as an EU citizen". Below this is the heading "All the initiatives you can support" and three initiative cards. Each card has a yellow "COLLECTION ONGOING" tag, a title, and a number of supporters.

Initiative	Supporters
Stop Cruelty Stop Slaughter	2,710
STOP FAKE FOOD: ORIGIN ON LABEL	948
Stop Destroying Videogames	365,291

Source: <https://citizens-initiative.europa.eu/en>

Existing e-Participation Tools at the EU level (Petitions Portal)

The Petitions Web Portal of the European Parliament is a platform allowing EU citizens, residents, and organizations to express their concerns and demands about EU policies. This system is distinct from the European Citizens' Initiative (ECI) as petitions are addressed to the European Parliament rather than the European Commission. Unlike the ECI, which sets the policy agenda and requires one million signatures, petitions do not have such stringent requirements. The Committee on Petitions (PETI) reviews the petitions and takes appropriate actions, such as referring them to other committees, preparing reports, or requesting investigations by the European Commission. However, the petition process faces challenges, including potential delays in the verification and handling of petitions, which could affect the overall efficiency of the system.

A screenshot of the Petitions Web Portal homepage. The header features the European Parliament logo and the text 'Petitions European Parliament'. Below the header is a navigation bar with links for 'Home', 'Find a petition', 'Start a petition', and 'Help'. The main content area starts with a 'Welcome to the Petitions Web Portal' heading, followed by a paragraph explaining the objective of the petitions process. Below this is a link to 'More about the objectives of the petitions process, the petitions committee and the petitions web portal'. The page is divided into three columns of featured content: 1. 'Welcome to the Petitions Web Portal' with a photo of a man in a suit and the EU flag. 2. 'Impact of the Committee on Petitions in the 9th legislative term (2019-2024)' with a graphic showing a globe and people. 3. 'REPORT on the outcome of the Committee on Petitions' deliberations during 2022' with a graphic of a notebook and a pen.

Source: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/petitions/en/home>

Existing e-Participation Tools at the EU level (Public Consultations)

Public consultations are a critical tool for e-participation within the European Union. They allow citizens, residents, and organizations to express their opinions and concerns regarding EU policies. Unlike the European Citizens' Initiative (ECI), public consultations do not require a specific number of signatures to be effective. Instead, they provide a more direct platform for individuals and groups to offer feedback on policy proposals that are within the EU's legislative scope.

These consultations are conducted primarily through the European Parliament, rather than the European Commission, and offer participants a way to influence existing policies. They differ from petitions in that they focus on gathering feedback and shaping policy rather than addressing specific grievances or concerns. Public consultations are an essential avenue for citizen involvement in the EU, but challenges such as potential delays in processing and verifying petitions can limit their effectiveness (European Commission, n.d.)

Read more for e-Participation

- https://www.un.org/esa/desa/papers/2020/wp163_2020.pdf
- <https://ideas.repec.org/a/rom/mancon/v11y2017i1p88-98.html>
- <https://europeanmovement.eu/policy/citizens-participation-in-the-digital-age-e-democracy/>
- <https://desapublications.un.org/sites/default/files/publications/2024-09/%28Web%20version%29%20E-Government%20Survey%202024%201392024.pdf>
- [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2016/556949/IPOL_STU\(2016\)556949_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2016/556949/IPOL_STU(2016)556949_EN.pdf)

Chapter 2

ICT tools Showcase/Practice and Use Case Analysis

For e-advocacy campaigns, technology plays a vital role in organizing, engaging, and driving change. Various tools and platforms are utilized across different functions to streamline communication, collect data, and spread the message effectively. Below is a refined list of the technology stack frequently used in e-advocacy initiatives:

- **Project Management:** Tools like Confluence, Trello, and Taiga are essential for coordinating projects, ensuring all stakeholders are on the same page, and managing timelines efficiently.
- **Messaging/Communication:** Platforms such as Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Telegram, Signal, and Slack are indispensable for real-time communication, both within teams and with the public.
- **Data/Opinion Gathering:** Tools like the European Data Portal, Open Data Institute, Cos4Cloud, and Google Forms are commonly employed to gather public opinions, conduct surveys, and collect critical data for informed advocacy.
- **Data Visualization:** Google Looker Studio, Infogram, and Datawrapper help transform raw data into comprehensible visual insights that can be shared with both stakeholders and the public.
- **Collaboration:** Platforms like Miro, Padlet, Figma, and Lucid enable teams to brainstorm, design, and collaborate on documents and visual content, making complex ideas more accessible.
- **Outreach:** WordPress, Vev, Wix, and social media platforms like TikTok and Facebook Pages are used to broadcast the campaign's message, reaching a broader audience. MailChimp helps with email campaigns, allowing personalized communication with supporters.
- **Fundraising:** Platforms like Kickstarter, GoFundMe, Patreon, and Ulule help raise necessary funds to keep advocacy campaigns running, often relying on grassroots support.
- **Petition Tools:** Platforms such as the European Citizens' Initiative (ECI), Change.org, Avaaz, and YouMove Europe enable the public to initiate or support petitions that press policymakers to take action.

Some proposed tools

miro

change.org

Get some data in...

Open Data

European data

data.europa.eu The official portal for European data

ODOUR
COLLECT

FreshWaterWatch
Powered by earthwatch
EUROPE

Cos4Cloud

TRAFIKLAB

EUROPEAN OPEN
SCIENCE CLOUD

Petitions

change.org

AVAAZ.ORG
THE WORLD IN ACTION

YOU MOVE
EUROPE

ecsa | European
Citizen Science
Association

Polls/Forms

Google Forms

SurveyMonkey

Open Data from EU

In the context of open data from the EU, several initiatives are underway to make data accessible to the public for use in research, civic engagement, and policy-making. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and platforms like the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) are examples of entities working toward integrating open data across scientific and civic domains. These organizations allow citizens and researchers alike to contribute and access large-scale datasets.

For instance, the **European Open Science Cloud** provides a collaborative environment where researchers and citizens can store, share, and process research data. The **Cos4Cloud** project is another initiative aimed at citizen science, allowing users to contribute environmental data via connected technologies.

Meanwhile, **National Access Points (NAPs)** provide traffic and mobility data across different EU member states, helping to inform public services and enhance transport policy-making. Each country offers its own portal, such as Greece's **NAP** at www.nap.gov.gr, or Belgium's at www.transportdata.be/en.

While open data initiatives are progressing, some of these systems are still in their early stages, particularly in terms of preparing data for Application Programming Interfaces (API)

consumption, which would allow developers to seamlessly integrate this data into various applications and tools.

National Access Points (NAPs)

Country	National Access Point
AT Austria	https://www.mobilitydata.gv.at/
BE Belgium	https://www.transportdata.be/en/
BG Bulgaria	https://lima.api.bg/
HR Croatia	https://www.promet-info.hr/
CY Republic of Cyprus	http://www.traffic4cyprus.org.cy/
CZ Czech Republic	https://data.gov.cz/datov%C3%A9-sady
DK Denmark	https://nap.vd.dk/
EE Estonia	http://www.peatus.ee/
FI Finland	http://www.finap.fi/
FR France	https://transport.data.gouv.fr/
DE Germany	https://mobilithek.info/
GR Greece	http://www.nap.gov.gr/
HU Hungary	https://napportal.kozut.hu/

Source: <https://www.trafiklab.se/>

Open Data API for Analytics

APIs, or Application Programming Interfaces, are tools that simplify communication between different software systems. They work by standardizing requests, ensuring that different systems can understand each other. When a request is made through the API, the receiving system processes it and sends back a reply. This process is particularly efficient, as it automates the interactions between systems, saving time and resources.

APIs are also beneficial because they use standardized protocols, making the data exchange reliable and uniform across different systems. This means that whether systems are using different platforms, they can still effectively communicate and share data. For example, when a user inputs a request via a browser to access data (as illustrated in the image), the API retrieves the relevant information and provides the output in a structured format, such as JSON. This process is critical for data analytics, as it enables access to large datasets that can be processed and analyzed in real-time (De, B., 2023).

Source: Trainer's elaboration

EU Petition Platforms

These platforms allow European citizens to create and support petitions directed towards European institutions such as the European Commission, the European Parliament, or even local governments.

Key Elements:

- Target Audience: The petition can be addressed to a range of authorities, from the local government to European bodies.
- Process of Creating a Petition: A petitioner must first define the petition's title and target audience. The platform provides a structured way to indicate the recipients, whether local or European decision-makers. Then, the petitioner outlines the desired action they want the targeted authority to take and explains why this is important.

- Campaigns Example: An example petition could involve campaigns like "Save the Alps' last glaciers!" directed at local governments to prevent further development in environmentally sensitive regions.

Target Audience: European Commission, European Parliament, Local Governments

These platforms empower EU citizens to actively engage in the legislative process by starting or supporting petitions directed towards key European institutions like the European Commission and Parliament.

Language of the campaign

English

You can only create your campaign in one language at a time. If you'd like your campaign published in more than one language, start by submitting the first language, then the second, etc.

Give your petition a title *

Who are you addressing? *

Enter this value following the structure in these examples: 'To the President of the European Parliament', 'To the Members of the European Parliament', 'To the President of the French state'.

You won't be able to change the target(s) of your petition once you set it to 'Published'.

This petition is run by *

Enter your name here

What do you want the petition target(s) to do? *

You won't be able to change your petition text once you set it to 'Published'.

Why is this important? *

Add an image

YOU MOVE EUROPE WHO ARE WE? YOU MOVE CAMPAIGNS START A CAMPAIGN LOG-IN HELP

Save the Alp's last glaciers!

ENGLISH

103,320 of 125,000 signatures

First name* Last name*

Your email*

Country* Postal code:

Are you a regular tourist to Tyrol. Yes No

Your comments:

Do you want to find out if this campaign is successful? *

- Yes! Let me know if this campaign is successful and how I can help quite in other relevant campaigns. If you have us your email, we may contact you to tell you more about how you can help us, including by supporting our work with a donation.
- No! I don't want to receive information about the progress of this campaign or other campaigns.

You can unsubscribe at any time. Just go to our unsubscribe page. By entering your information you confirm that you are at least 16 years old.

SIGN THE PETITION

Wellmove Europe is fighting for a better world, and we need barriers like you to help our community of more than 100,000 people. Already you're powering this campaign real, but by clicking "Yes", you'll receive a wider range of campaigns that need your help. Sign up to hear more and make your difference. If legally required in your country, we will send you an email to confirm entering your data on our site. By clicking "Yes", you're giving Wellmove Europe your consent to process your personal information. We might share your name, surname and country with the petition target. Unless you subscribe to receive personalised updates, we will delete your data after the campaign has ended. We will never share your data with any third parties without your permission. See our full privacy policy [here](#).

Recent comments

Save the alp's glaciers Neil

PETITION

The two largest glaciers in Tyrol's Alps are threatened by further development with ski lifts and slopes. We urge the Tyrol state government to halt the planned projects at the Pitztal and Kaunertal glaciers and to legally establish absolute glacier protection for the entire Tyrol region.

WHY IS THIS IMPORTANT?

Alpine glaciers are melting at an alarming rate. [1]

Now, these beautiful mountains face a **new threat: intensive tourism**. The local government in Austria

Source: <https://youmoveeurope.eu/en>

Petition Structure:

- Start by giving your petition a clear and concise title.
- Identify the decision-maker (for example, the European Commission or a specific local government).
- Outline the action you want the target to take, followed by a strong rationale explaining the importance of the issue.
- Add supporting images and links for more credibility.

The screenshot shows the change.org website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the change.org logo, "Start a petition", "My petitions", and "Browse". Below this, there is a search bar and a "Log in" link. The main content area features a "DECISION MAKER" section for the "European Commission". A red button labeled "Start a petition" is prominent. Below the button, there is a section for "AI-generated content" and a paragraph of text describing the European Commission's role. To the right of the text is a large image of the European Union flag. Below the main content, there is a section titled "Petitions directed towards European Commission" with two small thumbnail images: one showing a group of people with flags and another showing a woman speaking.

Once the petition gathers enough signatures, it is submitted to the relevant institution, where it can influence policy decisions.

The screenshot shows a change.org petition page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the change.org logo, "Start a petition", "My petitions", and "Browse". Below this, there is a search bar and a "Log in" link. The main content area features a petition titled "Sea rescue is non-negotiable - Open the ports for Sea-Watch 3!". The petition has a "Confirmed victory" badge and a sub-header "This petition made change with 89,046 supporters!". Below the sub-header, there is a large image of a boat on the water. To the right of the image, there are social media sharing buttons for Facebook, email, WhatsApp, and Twitter, along with a "Copy link" button. Below the image, there is a "Movement" section with the hashtag "#ChangingEurope19: European citizens take act...". The petition was started on January 22, 2019, and is directed to the "European Commission". Below this, there is a section titled "Why this petition matters" with a sub-header "Started by Anne and Sea-Watch e.V.". The text in this section discusses the EU's actions regarding Sea-Watch 3 and the impact on refugees.

Source: <https://www.change.org/>

Creating an Anonymized pre/post intervention Survey

To create an anonymized pre/post intervention survey, you can use Google Forms in combination with Google Sheets and Google Apps Script. Here's a step-by-step guide:

Step 1: Create a Google Spreadsheet

- Use Google Sheets as the datastore to hold unique tokens for each participant.
- Ensure that each token is unique and can be used to identify the same user across multiple surveys without revealing their identity.
- Example tokens could be numerical values such as 12345, 67890, etc.

Step 2: Create a Pre-Intervention Google Form

- Design your pre-intervention survey in Google Forms. Add a field labeled "Your unique token is:" for participants to enter their token.
- Use Google Apps Script to generate a unique token for each form submission. The script will add this token to your Google Spreadsheet after submission.

Step 3: Google Apps Script Integration

- Write a Google Apps Script that generates a unique token on form submission and stores it in your Google Sheet.

- The script should display the token to the participant after the pre-intervention survey submission. This token will then be used in the post-intervention survey for tracking.

Example Script:

```
javascript Copy code  
  
function generateToken() {  
  var sheet = SpreadsheetApp.getActiveSpreadsheet().getSheetByName("Tokens");  
  var lastRow = sheet.getLastRow();  
  var token = Math.floor(100000 + Math.random() * 900000); // Generates a random 6-dig  
  sheet.getRange(lastRow + 1, 1).setValue(token);  
  return token;  
}  
  
function onFormSubmit(e) {  
  var token = generateToken();  
  var formResponse = e.response;  
  formResponse.setCustomResponse("Your unique token is: " + token);  
}
```

Step 4: Post-Intervention Survey

- Create a second Google Form for the post-intervention survey, again including the "Your unique token is:" field.
- The user enters the same token they received during the pre-intervention survey.
- The script can check if the entered token exists in the Google Spreadsheet and allow the user to submit their post-intervention answers.

Step 5: Deploy the App

- Use Google Apps Script to deploy your script as a web app.
- Provide the generated link to the participants to access both the pre- and post-intervention surveys.
- Ensure that the spreadsheet and script permissions are set to allow public access for viewing and token generation.

By following these steps, you'll have an automated and anonymized system where users are identified by unique tokens across pre- and post-surveys without revealing their personal information.

Read more

https://citizens-initiative.europa.eu/sites/default/files/202409/ECI%20Advocacy%20Handbook_EN.pdf

<https://ddc.dk/>

<https://www.trafiklab.se/api/other-apis/public-transport-europe/>

<https://www.ecsa.ngo/>

<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>

<https://saveyourinternet.eu/>

<https://edri.org/>

<https://eu-citizen.science/> Chapter 3.

Chapter 3

Introduction to design thinking/ideation & its Roles in e-Advocacy & e-Participation

Design thinking is an iterative, user-centered approach used to solve real-world problems, often complex, elusive, and subjective. This process involves engaging multiple stakeholders, including state, community, businesses, and citizens, in addressing social challenges. The core stages—discover, define, develop, and deliver—help teams systematically explore and refine solutions through collaboration and experimentation. By focusing on real-life challenges, design thinking encourages non-linear thinking and promotes flexibility, making it a powerful tool for initiatives like e-Advocacy.

The process is not a one-size-fits-all model but an evolving cycle that adapts as more information and feedback become available. It begins with discovering the problem through research and empathy. This step involves gathering information, identifying the stakeholders' needs, and defining the root causes. Following this, the define phase distills insights from the discovery process, focusing on the most critical aspects of the problem to address.

Once the problem is clearly defined, the team moves into the develop phase, where ideas are generated, prototyped, and tested. This stage relies on divergent thinking to brainstorm various solutions and convergent thinking to narrow them down to the most promising options. As solutions take shape, they are validated through user testing and feedback, leading to multiple iterations that refine the design. This cyclical movement between ideation and testing ensures the solution is relevant and effective.

Finally, the deliver phase focuses on implementing the refined solution, ensuring it meets the target audience's needs. The design is tested in real-world scenarios to validate its impact. At this stage, the solution is ready for deployment and scaling, accompanied by continuous feedback loops for future improvements.

A key aspect of design thinking is empathy, which enables teams to understand the user's experiences, frustrations, and aspirations. Tools like empathy maps and user stories help teams visualize and contextualize these insights, ensuring the solution remains grounded in real human experiences. This approach fosters a deeper connection between designers and end-users, aligning the final output with the users' actual needs.

Empathy Map Canvas

Designed for:

Designed by:

Date:

Version:

Last updated on 16 July 2017. Download a copy of this canvas at <http://gamestorming.com/empathy-map/>

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Source: <https://medium.com/@davegray/updated-empathy-map-canvas-46df22df3c8a>

The **Double Diamond model** of design thinking, a non-linear and iterative process used to explore, define, and solve complex problems. The first diamond represents the process of understanding and defining the problem, while the second represents creating solutions and refining them through prototyping and validation.

Source:

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Design-Thinking-Double-diamond-scheme-applied-in-ARP-courses_fig1_319342653

The stages are as follows:

- **Research & Empathy:** Investigating the problem and empathizing with users to gain insights.
- **Define:** Narrowing down the findings to define the core problem.
- **Ideate & Prototype:** Brainstorming and developing ideas, creating prototypes to test.
- **Validation:** Iterating based on feedback and validating the solution.

This model emphasizes the importance of iteration, refining ideas, and ensuring that solutions are tested and validated before being implemented. It's highly useful for tackling ambiguous, complex problems with no clear solutions from the start.

4-stage Model of the British Design Council The 4D's Model includes four main phases:

- **Discover:** Identifying the problem and its scope.
- **Define:** Describing and framing the solution.
- **Develop:** Developing the actual solution through iterative testing and improvement.
- **Deliver:** Presenting and implementing the solution.
- This model provides a structured framework for tackling design problems from concept to delivery.

Source: <https://www.designcouncil.org.uk/news-opinion/double-diamond-universally-accepted-depiction-design-process>

Source: *Trainer's elaboration*

Ideation - Pivoting (Decoupling/Unbundling)

Pivoting refers to adapting and adjusting a core idea by exploring new connections and reimagining steps in a process. Through decoupling or unbundling, teams can break down complex problems into more manageable parts, allowing for flexibility and fresh combinations. This method simplifies the problem-solving process and increases the flexibility of ideas. The pivot occurs when new steps are introduced or existing ones are modified to enhance the original concept, creating a dynamic and iterative process that moves projects forward.

Source: *Trainer's elaboration*

Read more: <https://www.lennysnewsletter.com/p/the-art-of-the-pivot-part-2-how-why>

Co-creation: Les Éclaireurs “The Frontliners” Case Study

Aim:

To enhance public service by making it more appealing, democratic, and efficient.

Citizen-Centered Innovation

Public services are redesigned to reflect the genuine needs and experiences of citizens, fostering a more inclusive and democratic approach.

Creative Problem-Solving

Creative and innovative tools replace traditional methods to identify and address systemic issues in public service delivery.

Future-Oriented Thinking

This approach focuses on anticipating future challenges by exploring how public authorities can evolve to meet new needs.

Collaborative Design

By uniting experts, practitioners, and stakeholders, Les Éclaireurs initiates a co-creation process to brainstorm and test new ideas in real-world conditions.

Methodology:

- **Initial Group Discussion:** A group of participants, including researchers, experts, and practitioners, collaborates with designers and public policy specialists. They identify major controversies around the chosen topic, summarizing key information for further development.
- **Exploration of Blind Spots and Ideation:** Participants dive into overlooked areas of the topic, collectively brainstorming new ideas, solutions, and tools to address these gaps.
- **Scenario Creation and Restitution Workshop:** Designers and policy experts transform these ideas into an illustrative scenario, presented in a restitution workshop for further discussion.
- **Field Testing:** Volunteer groups test portions of the scenario within their own administration and real-world conditions, gaining practical insights into the effectiveness of the proposed solutions.

Read more

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/216694554_eParticipation_in_Europe_Current_State_and_Practical_Recommendations_in_E-Government_Success_Around_the_World_Cases_Empirical_Studies_and_Practical_Recommendations

https://ijab.de/fileadmin/redaktion/PDFs/Shop_PDFs/Guidelines_eParticipation_engl.pdf

<https://ecas.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/Eparticipation-Guidelines.pdf>

https://issuu.com/e-governanceacademy/docs/ecitizeni_manual_english

https://ddc.dk/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Missionplaybook_A4.pdf

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319342653_Design_Thinking_as_a_methodology_for_solving_problems_contributions_from_academia_to_society

<https://www.designorate.com/category/design-management/>

Chapter 4

Action Planning and Role Play

SWOT Analysis

Why use SWOT?

SWOT analysis helps identify internal and external factors that can impact the success of an e-Advocacy campaign.

Strengths: Internal attributes that positively contribute to the campaign's goals.

Examples: Strong social media presence, motivated volunteers.

Weaknesses: Internal limitations that may hinder the campaign's success.

Examples: Limited resources, lack of technical know-how.

Opportunities: External factors that the campaign can leverage for better outcomes.

Examples: Increased public awareness, favorable government policies.

Threats: External challenges that could negatively affect the campaign.

Examples: Political opposition, economic instability.

SWOT ANALYSIS

Source:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SWOT_analysis#/media/File:SWOT_en.svg

“The Waste Management Bill”

The role-play scenario titled "The Waste Management Bill" introduces participants to a complex local issue with multiple stakeholders. The setting is a fictional mountainous village near a river, emphasizing the real-world challenges of waste disposal in sensitive environmental areas. Participants take on roles from various perspectives, representing both pro- and anti-disposal facility groups, grassroots movements, and the Community Advisory Council (CAC).

The activity is structured into several phases:

Phase 1: Introduction and Setup

Teams:

- Advocacy Group supporting the waste disposal facility (government-aligned NGO)
 - Advocacy Group opposing the facility (environmental NGO)
 - Citizen’s grassroots movement against the facility
 - Community Advisory Council (CAC)
- Facilitator: Local Government passing the bill.

Each team represents a different stakeholder group with varying motivations and concerns about the waste disposal facility.

Phase 2: Discover (Empathy & Research) – 10 minutes

- Team Activity: Each group researches their stakeholders' positions, focusing on their needs, concerns, and motivations.
- Group Activity: Participants fill out an empathy map for an average citizen affected by the facility, mapping out what the citizen sees, hears, thinks, and feels regarding the project.

Phase 3: Define – 10 minutes

- Team Activity: Groups define the core problems or opportunities posed by the waste management bill from their perspectives.
- Presentation: Each group presents their findings and compares overlaps and differences with the other groups, facilitating an open discussion about the bill.

Phase 4: Develop (Ideation & Solution Design) – 15 minutes

- Team Activity: Participants brainstorm or brainwrite potential solutions or actions to address the concerns raised by stakeholders. This process promotes collaboration and allows quieter voices to contribute equally.

Phase 5: Deliver (Present & Negotiate) – 15 minutes

- Team Activity: Each group creates a tangible action plan representing their proposed solutions. These are presented to the group, simulating real-world negotiation and compromise between conflicting interests.

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Read more

https://www.un.org/esa/desa/papers/2020/wp163_2020.pdf

<https://ideas.repec.org/a/rom/mancon/v11y2017i1p88-98.html>

<https://europeanmovement.eu/policy/citizens-participation-in-the-digital-age-e-democracy/>

<https://desapublications.un.org/sites/default/files/publications/2024-09/%28Web%20version%29%20E-Government%20Survey%202024%201392024.pdf>

[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2016/556949/IPOL_STU\(2016\)556949_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2016/556949/IPOL_STU(2016)556949_EN.pdf)

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